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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a paradigm shift in the technology. AI has the potential to transform the parameters of scientific research, challenges before the humans. Rapid industrialization, urbanization and the fascination towards the economic growth increases threats to environment. The effects of the climate change affecting the human life by various ways. The pattern of precipitation, rise in temperature, sea level rise, biodiversity loss these are the major issues of concern. Discovery of the AI tools brought new hope and opportunity to look into the problems of the environment and provide scientifically proven solution which will be beyond human's emotional and less practical thinking pattern. This research paper will focus on the major environmental challenges and the use of Artificial Intelligent to help to minimize the problems of the environment. There are high hopes that artificial intelligence (AI) can help tackle some of the world's biggest environmental problems.

Key words: Artificial Intelligence, Environment, Climate change, Technology

Introduction

Technology changes the way human thinks. Major changes in the society and mind set of the human has a technology as a driven force behind it. Technology divides generations from one another. History of civilization impacted most by the technological research and advancement in the science field. Industrial revolution has started the process of paradigm shift in the technical arena. World Wide Web has triggered the process of globalization. The process of technical advancement which is culminated in the 21st century with the discovery of Artificial Intelligence tool, yet there are many discoveries yet to come to make human life easier and comfortable. In this capacity, it provides us with unparalleled convenience, efficiency, and connectivity, empowering us to perform tasks more easily, communicates across vast distances, and accesses a wealth of information at our fingertips.

The decade of 70s marked the decade of the unrest and turbulence. The 1970s was a decade of technological advancements, inflation, stagnant wages, energy crises, geopolitical uncertainty, war, rebellious youth, and political scandal and environmental concern. Development issues must be seen as a crucial issue from the point of the economy and political systems of the countries. The agenda of the development gained the center point at that time. Most of the countries especially western developed and eastern developing countries followed the path of the development. Industrialization and rapid urbanization elevates the speed of the development. With the rapid Industrialization and urbanization creates the problem of the environment. The environment is where we all live; and development is what we all do in attempting to improve our lot within that abode. The two are inseparable and the path of the industrialization was always environmentally unsustainable. Climate disasters, such as climate change, pollution, loss of biodiversity, deforestation, water scarcity, land degradation, global warming, glacier melting, and sea-level rise posing a serious threat to human life and the global ecosystem.

Environmental Challenges

The decade of 70's saw the era of agitations. United Nations (UN) uplifted some major issues of great concern which could be harmful for the world society. UN provided the platform for the mitigation and greater cooperation on these issues. The 1972 UN Conference on the Human Environment brought the industrialized and developing nations together to solve the environmental issues for the sustainable life for future generations. The major environmental issues after the 70s seen as follows

Pollution Monitoring and Control

Pollution monitoring refers to the systematic observation and measurement of environmental pollutants. It involves using various tools, sensors, and analytical techniques to detect pollutants' presence and concentration. Key types of pollution monitoring include:

1. Air Quality Monitoring: Measures pollutants such as particulate matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}), nitrogen oxides (NO_x),

sulfur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and volatile organic compounds (VOCs).

2. Water Quality Monitoring: Involves testing for physical, chemical, and biological water quality parameters such as pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), nitrates, phosphates, heavy metals, and microbial contamination.
3. Soil Pollution Monitoring: Focuses on detecting contaminants like heavy metals, pesticides, hydrocarbons, and industrial waste in soil.

Climate Change

Climate change refers to long-term changes in temperature, precipitation, wind patterns, and other elements of the Earth's climate system. It is primarily driven by human activities, especially the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and industrial processes, leading to increased concentrations of greenhouse gases (GHGs) such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O) in the atmosphere. These gases trap heat in earth's atmosphere which cause rise in global temperatures and resulted in environmental impacts.

Biodiversity and Wildlife Protection

Biodiversity refers to the variety and variability of life on Earth, including species diversity, genetic diversity, and ecosystem diversity. It provides critical ecosystem services like food, medicine, clean air, and water. Biodiversity is vital for maintaining ecosystem resilience, enabling ecosystems to adapt to environmental changes and disturbances.

Water Management and Conservation

Water management and conservation encompass a variety of practices and policies that balance the needs of humans and ecosystems, while ensuring sustainable water use for future generations. Water management and conservation involve strategies and practices to efficiently use, maintain, and improve water quality, especially in agricultural, industrial, and urban settings.

Deforestation

Deforestation refers to the large-scale removal of trees from forested areas, leading to a permanent change in land use. It can have severe environmental impacts on environment such as biodiversity loss, loss of habitat for animal, changes in precipitation, rise in the temperature, rise in the sea level, rise in soil erosion.

What is Artificial Intelligence?

Artificial intelligence (AI) is technology that enables computers and machines to simulate human learning, comprehension, problem solving, decision making, creativity and autonomy. Applications and devices equipped with AI can see and identify objects. They can understand and respond to human language. They can learn from new information and experience. They can make detailed recommendations to users and experts. They can act independently, replacing the need for human intelligence or intervention. Stanford researcher John McCarthy first used the term 'Artificial Intelligence' in a workshop held at Dartmouth in 1956, and this workshop marked the beginning of

artificial intelligence research. AI is a broad field that encompasses many different disciplines, including computer science, data analytics and statistics, hardware and software engineering, linguistics, neuroscience, and even philosophy and psychology.

How Artificial Intelligence works?

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a combination of the various streams such as computer science, statistics, language philosophy, psychology. AI works by using algorithms and models to simulate human-like intelligence and decision-making. It involves several processes and techniques that allow computers to analyze data, learn from it, make decisions, and even improve their performance over time. AI helps researchers, government bodies, organizations to process the data over the internet and simplify it to be use in application. Decision making process became easier, time consuming and with less human resources.

AI is a growing industry. Future world will become more reliable on the various applications of AI. Machines in AI replaced humans and animals. It is opposed to natural intelligence. AI explains its characteristics through an intelligence agent (Valle-Cruz et al., 2019)

AI and Environmental challenges

The battle against environmental challenges has intensified in recent years, demanding innovative solutions. AI applications have provided the platform to give solutions for these environmental challenges.

AI and Biodiversity conservation

Biodiversity hotspots are the geographical area where biodiversity is vanishing due to the destruction, human intervention. Due to this lots of species are on the verge of extinction. With the use of the AI it will be possible to stop the extinction of the plant and animal species. Nature serves Map of Biodiversity Importance is using AI to find such places of biologically important for saving this species.

AI and Climate change

Climate change is a big challenge before humans. One of the UNEP led initiative inside the World Environment Situation Room launched in 2022 is working as the international methane emissions observatory which uses AI to monitoring and mitigating methane emissions. Green Horizon Project from IBM which monitors data and suggest pollution reducing tactics. Google Map is also a AI tool which uses the real time traffic data and is useful to optimize navigation and can be used to save fuel for coming generation.

AI and Agriculture

Climate change impacted most agriculture sector. Changing precipitation pattern and changed temperature affected the crop yielding which is a major concern for the farmer, the government and the society as a whole. The role of AI in agriculture is to improve farming and make it advance which will be helpful in food sustainability. AI based applications help farmer in monitoring soil moisture pH levels and essential nutrient contents which will ensure sustainable agriculture practices. AI can improve weather forecasting

in agriculture which helps farmer in making decisions about planting irrigation.

AI and Air

Artificial intelligence would be beneficial for air quality. AI powered applications can be developed to measure the pollution level in the specific areas and these tools can detect the pollution level and give warning to the people living in that area so that people can take care of this and resulted in good health. Environmental monitoring initiative that UNEP has co-founded in partnership with IQAir is the GEMS Air Pollution Monitoring platform it is the largest air quality information network in the world. It uses AI to look into the impact of real time air quality which helps people in protecting health issues.

Conclusion:

Environmental challenges encompass a wide range of issues, including climate change, pollution, deforestation, biodiversity loss, water scarcity, and waste management. Artificial Intelligence (AI) can help address these challenges in several ways. AI's potential in addressing environmental challenges is significant, but it also requires careful consideration of data privacy, energy consumption, and equitable access to AI technologies. Every technology has its pros and cons. AI can transform the way we monitor and analyze the data is remarkable it is time consuming and uses less human resources. AI has the potential to transform the way of living. AI will play a larger role in environment related issues.

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